

Social Labs in Action: A Practical Handbook for Cultural Heritage Buildings

Inherit

Purpose of this handbook

This handbook provides a concise, practical guide for planning and implementing Social Labs in cultural heritage (CH) contexts. It is designed to help practitioners **structure participatory processes, engage diverse user groups and co-create solutions** for sustainable and meaningful reuse of heritage spaces.

Insights from the INHERIT project underpin the handbook's approach. Through the project, Social Labs were implemented across eight cultural heritage pilot sites in Europe, generating practical experience and lessons learned. These insights are combined with **stakeholder engagement methodologies**, the principles of social responsibility (ISO 26000), and the core values of the New European Bauhaus (NEB).

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What are Social Labs?

Social Labs in cultural heritage contexts are **collaborative, experimental settings** embedded in real cultural heritage environments. Stakeholders from science, innovation, cultural heritage practice and civil society can come together in these labs to **co-create and test solutions** grounded in a shared understanding of the problem.

Why Social Labs?

Cultural heritage thrives when people help shape its future. Social Labs recognise and build on local knowledge, ensuring **solutions are socially relevant, inclusive and future-proof**. They turn CH buildings into living spaces of innovation that combine sustainability, culture, and community engagement. These frameworks help Social Labs balance technological innovation with social value, heritage preservation and community well-being.

Stakeholder mapping and involvement

A Social Lab begins with an **iterative stakeholder mapping** process. This starts with desk research and internal brainstorming to identify relevant stakeholder groups, followed by the identification of specific actors and potential end users. Stakeholder mapping is not a one-time exercise but is continuously refined throughout the project to reflect evolving roles, interests and levels of influence.

Stakeholders are individuals or organisations with an interest in or influence over the project and its objectives. End users are those who directly use or benefit from the developed solutions. Stakeholder representation follows the **Quadruple Helix model**, including public authorities, business and industry, research and education institutions, and civil society. Depending on the context, players from cultural and creative industries, media and the construction sector may also be involved.

Collaboration may take different forms, including co-design (jointly defining problems and approaches), co-creation (developing solutions together), and co-production (implementing agreed activities). Engagement can range from information and consultation to involvement and collaboration. Particular attention is given to owners, operators and decision-makers, vulnerable or underrepresented groups, and actors responsible for the long-term management of the cultural heritage site to ensure **inclusive and sustainable outcomes**.

Step-by-step guide for effective Social Labs

Below is an outline of the **4-step approach for designing and implementing Social Labs** in cultural heritage contexts, as defined in the **INHERIT Social Labs Methodological Handbook**.

1. Understand the context

A Social Lab starts with a structured context and needs analysis. This includes examining:

- heritage protection and conservation constraints
- legal and governance frameworks
- management structures
- social and community needs
- environmental and energy challenges
- cultural values of the site.

The aim is to identify the key issues to be addressed, such as adaptive re-use options, accessibility barriers, governance improvements or opportunities for social value creation. This step creates a shared understanding of the site's challenges and transformation potential.

How INHERIT did this

In INHERIT, this phase was supported through bilateral interviews, desk research and early stakeholder involvement. The findings informed the stakeholder engagement strategy and shaped the objectives of the first Social Lab workshops.

2. Workshops

Workshops represent the core of the Social Lab process. They bring together stakeholders to identify priorities and develop concrete proposals. These may include re-use concepts, governance innovations, service improvements, prototypes, community initiatives or pilot actions. To support this process, structured methods such as World Cafes and Mapping Walks are applied.

Workshops explicitly connect outcomes to social responsibility frameworks and to the priorities identified during stakeholder mapping. They foster cross-sector dialogue and support the development of socially robust and context-sensitive solutions.

How INHERIT did this

In INHERIT, each pilot organised a kick-off workshop using the World Café method. Several pilots additionally implemented mapping walks to engage local communities. These activities generated initial lab projects, clarified governance challenges and established pathways for co-creation.

World Café

A facilitated conversational method in which participants rotate between small discussion tables to discuss and think about predefined questions. It enables **collective knowledge generation** and helps identify shared priorities and challenges without predefining solutions.

Mapping Walk

A participatory method where stakeholders **explore the heritage site** or its surrounding neighbourhood together, identifying spatial dynamics, assets, challenges and community perspectives. Variations of this method may include neighbourhood mapping, asset mapping or structured transect walks.

3. Pilot test and experiment

This phase translates proposals into practical action. Selected concepts are **tested in real-world settings** to assess feasibility and impact. Experiments may involve testing digital tools, piloting adaptive re-use concepts, trialling governance improvements, implementing cultural or educational events, or conducting small-scale interventions.

The focus is on evaluating both **technical performance and social dimensions**, including accessibility, inclusiveness, governance quality and user experience. Testing in real conditions ensures that solutions are context-sensitive and socially robust.

How INHERIT did this

Pilots were encouraged to test technological services alongside co-designed social initiatives, including community-driven activities.

4. Reflect and assess

This phase focuses on **structured reflection and learning**. Stakeholders assess what worked, what needs adjustment and what impacts were observed. Reflection strengthens transparency, shared ownership and continuous improvement.

This phase is linked to the **social life-cycle assessment (S-LCA)**, which assesses social responsibility performance and societal impact over the whole project lifecycle. The Multi-Stakeholder Forum provides additional expert feedback and cross-disciplinary review.

How INHERIT did this

Reflection was conducted through co-assessment workshops, MSF feedback sessions and S-LCA monitoring cycles, ensuring systematic evaluation of both social and technical outcomes.

Conclusion

A Social Lab is an **iterative learning process**. Context analysis, co-design, experimentation and reflection are continuously refined based on feedback and evolving conditions. Through repeated cycles, solutions become more robust, inclusive and widely supported.

The full study “Social Labs Methodological Handbook, High-Level Requirements” is available on the INHERIT website.

Authors:

Olga Bolibok, Pamela Bartar (ZSI),
Dimitra Aglamisi (UPCR),
Sofia Francescutto (ICONS)

Graphic Design: Lorenzo Cannella (ICONS)

Deliverable authors:

Pamela Bartar, Philipp Brugner (ZSI); Małgorzata
Ćwikła (ICLEI) Stamatia Rizou, Antonia Vronti (SLG),
Nesrin Senbuttermilch, Rexhina Merkohitaj (ZSI).

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For questions and
additional information
contact us at:

info@inheritproject.eu